

CULTURE PABLIK RILEYSHNZ – PR (PUBLIC RELATIONS) AND ADVERTISING

Annotation

This article examines the dynamics of the non-existence of public relations-PR (public relations) as a science. The role of public opinion in establishing the activities of organizations is indicated. The functions of public relations – PR are covered, such as the study of public opinion and its observation, monitoring of public movement, ensuring two-way interest between the organization and the public.

Key words: public opinion, public relations, intergovernmental relations, social life, industrial relations, Financial relations, International relations, consumer relations, statistics and research, mass media, etc.

Аннотация

В этой статье рассматривается динамика существования паблик рилейшнз – **PR** (связи с общественностью) как науки. Указывается на рол общественного мнения в установлении деятельности организаций. Охватываются функции паблик рилейшнз – **PR**, такие как изучение общественного мнения и его наблюдение, наблюдение за общественным движением, обеспечение двустороннего интереса между организацией и общественностей.

Ключевие слова: общественное мнение, связи с общественностью, межправительственные отношения, социальная жизнь, производственные отношения, финансовые отношения, международные отношения, отношения с потребителями, статистика и исследования, СМИ и т.д.

The term “Public Relations” (Public Relations – PR, PR) taken from the English language means “Public Relations”, “Public Relations”, “Public Relations”. This expression was first used by the third president of the USA, Thomas Jefferson. He mentioned this term for the first time in 1807 in his “Seventh Address to Congress”. The purpose of this was to raise the relations of the government with the public to the level of the state, to establish scientific and organizational aspects.

One of the founders of PR, Edward Bernays, defined the essence of this phrase as “action in the public interest”. So, it becomes clear that “the emergence of public relations in the United States is a direct product of political processes”. A century later, the history of PR, which became a reality as a separate science, originates from the events of that time. The following words of Thomas Jefferson, who became famous as a democrat, became a slogan for a number of newspapers that chose the path of democracy: “If I am told to have government and no newspapers, or newspapers and no government – choose one. I would say without hesitation that there should be newspapers even if there is no government”.

This opinion should not be interpreted unilaterally. It is possible that Thomas Jefferson envisioned increasing the position and responsibility of newspapers, which could play an important role in strengthening public relations. It can be seen that the democratic leader expressed for a specific purpose that the public relations of the government or any organization cannot be imagined without

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the press and mass media. In fact, "the social nature of the press, from the point of view of its main functions, is clearly visible in its other characteristic - the representative of public opinion," writes Mukhtar Khudoykulov, professor of the Faculty of Journalism of UzMU. reflecting his spiritual life and acting as an active factor in the mutual influence of social existence and social consciousness, he acts on the basis of public opinion in this regard" [1].

Studying the opinion of the public is an important criterion in relations with it. In practice, the term "function" refers to tasks that perform this activity. According to V. Korolko, public relations, in general, performs 3 main functions:

1. Studying public opinion and monitoring it. Through PR, it is possible to study the opinion of the public and to influence it effectively. If the public opinion is not studied in time, then the positive goal will not be achieved.

2. Monitoring public behavior. Therefore, it is important not only to study the opinion of the public, but also to monitor its actions. Pierman should find out how he behaves in this or that public action. As new situations arise, as social moods change, it is necessary to know in advance how the public behaves, in which direction the opinion of the publicist is changing. Accuracy plays an important role in the work of a public relations officer.

3. Ensuring mutual benefit between the organization and the public. It is necessary to develop cooperation with the public by ensuring not one-sided, but two-way interests. In this case, the cooperation will have a double benefit.

These three main functions are very important for a PR manager to develop public relations.

PR serves to establish public relations of organizations in society. As Sam Black writes, it focuses on the following ten main goals. That is:

1. Public opinion;
2. Public relations;
3. Intergovernmental relations;
4. Social life;
5. Industrial relations;
6. Financial relations;
7. International relations;
8. Relations with consumers;
9. Statistics and research;
10. Mass media[2].

The organization can establish relations with the external environment in different directions. Management of external communication flows of the organization is often aimed at coordination of public opinion about the organization, its reputation and formed image. In this regard, many things are important for the cultural manager - the work of establishing relations between the organization and the public. This type of relationship is directly addressed by the public relations service, or in other words, PR (public relations).

Public relations or PR is an activity that does not have a literal translation of the name into Uzbek, but its most common synonym is "public relations". Currently, the art of managing the communication process is being implemented in the field of public relations, which is increasingly considered a type of marketing. Public relations (PR) is a field of communicative activity aimed at "organizing a communicative space in a mode favorable to the object of PR." It is understood as "a management function that establishes and maintains mutually beneficial relations" [3].

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The communicative space in which PR activities are carried out can be fully included in the media sphere. With the help of mass media channels, messages are sent to a mass audience, which includes guests and competitors of cultural institutions, as well as other interested layers of society (authorities, artists, creators, representatives of art and culture, etc.). PR activities are an integral part of the management system of any organization, including non-profit ones, because:

- ✓ the market (including the leisure market) is saturated with goods and services;
- ✓ the needs of listeners, consumer requirements are increasingly differentiated;
- ✓ competition between firms working with similar consumers is growing.

In this regard, the importance of non-price competitive factors that create positive images, strengthen the organization's reputation and increase its popularity is increasingly important. These include communication process management technologies (advertising, branding, PR technologies, etc.). The external environment is the main vector on which all the efforts of PR technologists or managers for the development of the organization are directed. Nevertheless, all elements of the external and internal spheres somehow affect the work of the organization, which means that activities in different directions are necessary [3].

The main principles of activity in the field of PR are as follows: openness, clarity and timeliness of information; abandoning the subjective position; forming a certain opinion in society. Public relations as an organized activity can serve various purposes, especially in politics, which is most popular in Uzbekistan. In this regard, we consider a number of PR areas that can be most useful for cultural institutions.

1. Positioning is related to creating and maintaining the image or appearance of a cultural institution, cultural and art institute, cultural region, etc. Dislocations that are understandable to the audience and consumers. Otherwise, this object may not be different from others like it. In the positioning process, – answers must be given why the service (or organization, cultural and tourism region) exists, for which audience it is intended, why someone might be interested in buying it.

2. The goal is to form or permanently maintain the necessary opinions and ideas among consumers about a certain object (for example, a cultural event, cultural service, cultural institution), this region or this cultural service. depends. The main goal of a manager responsible for public relations is to achieve a high public reputation of a cultural institution, a certain creative person or a cultural region.

One of the great features of PR, as well as some other communication technologies, is that it is not about creating new messages, but about creating communicative contexts. Therefore, the purpose of PR activities also indirectly affects the mass audience, which is carried out through the symbolic processing of messages.

The tasks of PR activities in the field of culture include:

- ❖ study of public opinion about the cultural institution (creative community, etc.);
- ❖ interactions with mass media (sending press releases, etc.);
- ❖ organization of presentations and other events that shape public opinion about the cultural institution;
- ❖ implementation of measures aimed at strengthening social relations with partners and administrations;

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❖ participation in the process of forming the circle of friends of the cultural institution, boards of trustees and other structures that increase the reputation of the institution and form a positive image.

At the same time, in order to form a certain point of view among the target audience (for example, in relation to a certain theater), the specialist must take into account all the cultural characteristics (values, ideals, taste), psychological, socio-economic factors of this type of audience. and certain messages should be transmitted at a more convenient time and place. In addition, public relations activities, as a rule, are closely related to the mass media institution, so its success depends to a large extent on knowing how various media (print, television, radio, Internet) work [4].

Among the work vectors in the field of PR, the following can be noted:

- ✚ press relations, interviews, joint visits to the organization, round talks, etc.;
- ✚ preparation of press releases, letters to the editor;
- ✚ conducting press conferences, receptions and business meetings;
- ✚ participation in the creation or organization of photographs, advertisements, documentary films;
- ✚ finding positive associations based on the phenomenon of feelings, emotions;
- ✚ presentations, open doors, receptions, cultural services, exhibitions, souvenirs, holidays, etc.) to "attract" and permanently retain a potential consumer;
- ✚ organization of expositions at exhibitions and fairs (place, staff, catalog, booklet, etc.).

Much in the field of culture, where human services are performed, depends on the employees who, consciously or unconsciously, form a general opinion about the cultural institution. Therefore, in communication management, great attention is paid to the personal interaction of employees with visitors. Employees, in fact, play a key role in PR activities (for example, if they respond to the attitude of going, the consumer says that he should not visit because he has not visited this establishment). One of the tasks of managing cultural institutions is to ensure that employees understand the importance of public relations to the achievement of the goals of the organization as a whole. The rest of the PR-advertising activity only fills the general opinion about the cultural institution.

References:

- 1) Eshbekov To'liqin. Jamoatchilik bilan aloqalar va axborot xizmatlari. O'quv qo'llanma. –T.: O'zMU, 2012. – 80 b.
- 2) Bekmurodov M. O'zbekistonda jamoatchilik fikri. –T.: Fan, 1999. -162 b.
- 3) Gundarin M.V. Teoriya i praktika svyazey s obshchestvennostyu: osnovi media-rileyshnz. Ucheb. posobiye. –M.: Forum: infra-m, 2011.- 264 b.
- 4) Blek S. Vvedeniye v pablik rileyshnz. Ucheb. posobiye –Rostov-na-Donu, 1998.- 196 b.